

was 5 cm throughout the growing season.

Plant height and tillers per pot were significantly higher with rice husk. Thirty days after transplanting, growth response to burned husk was significantly better than to unburned husk (Table 1), perhaps because unburned husk decomposes more slowly. At later growth, both treatments performed similarly. The trend was similar for panicle number, spikelets per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, and grain yield (Table 2). Compared with the control, plants yielded 22% more with unburned husk and 25% more with burned husk. *ℒ*

Table 1. Effect of rice husk on rice plant height and tillering in rice. Sabah, Malaysia.

Treatment	Plant height ^a (cm)			Tillers (no./pot)	
	30 DT	60 DT	90 DT	30 DT	60 DT
No rice husk	20 c	30 b	46 b	15 c	25 b
Unburned rice husk	26 b	59 a	73 a	23 b	50 a
Burned rice husk	31 a	60 a	74 a	30 a	52 a

^a Means with a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Table 2. Effect of rice husk on yield components and rice grain yield. ^a Sabah, Malaysia.

Treatment	Panicles (no.)	Spikelets per panicle	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (g/pot)
No rice husk	25 b	58 b	18 b	180 b
Unburned rice husk	35 a	68 a	22 a	200 a
Burned rice husk	36 a	70 a	23 a	202 a

^a Means with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Effect of organic N fractions in submerged soil on rice yield

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Applied N fertilizer becomes part of soil N. Soil N, although modified by applied N, plays the dominant role in N nutrition for rice. In a 1983-84 wet season experiment, we found that hydrolyzable soil N (using 6 N HCl extractant) at 15, 30, 45, and 60 d after transplanting (DT) was positively and significantly related to rice grain yield (see table), indicating that the hydrolyzable soil N fraction is highly important to N nutrition in submerged rice soil. Nonhydrolyzable soil N was negatively related to grain yield at 60 DT. *ℒ*

Relation between rice yield and the hydrolyzable and nonhydrolyzable soil N fractions, Pantnagar, India.

Parameter	Regression equation ^a	<i>r</i> ^b
<i>Hydrolyzable soil N</i>		
15 DT	$Y = 525 + 1.908 X$	0.912**
30 DT	$Y = 1511 + 1.236 X$	0.857**
45 DT	$Y = 1586 + 1.262 X$	0.884**
60 DT	$Y = 1445 + 1.481 X$	0.572*
<i>Nonhydrolyzable soil N</i>		
60 DT	$Y = 5994 - 3.114 X$	-0.553*

^a *Y* = grain yield, *X* = respective organic N fraction. ^b Significant 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Effect of onset of monsoon on length of growing season and productivity of rainfed rice in Madhya Pradesh

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In Madhya Pradesh, India, rice is grown in about 4.7 million ha, of which 80% is rainfed. Rice yields are about 1.0 t/ha and depend entirely on the monsoon.

Analysis of 80 yr (1901-80) of rainfall data from Raipur Station showed that the monsoon usually begins 11-17 Jun

on 24th standard meteorological wk. We used daily rainfall data from 1941 to 1981 to determine the probability of early (19%), normal (34%) and late (47%) onset of monsoon.

Rainfed rice depends entirely on rainfall. Length of rainy season determines the optimum duration of rice varieties. From 40-yr data, we calculated the average length of the growing season under early, normal, and late onset of monsoon (see figure) and averaged the rice productivity for the corresponding years (see table).

Data in the table suggest that early duration varieties are best for this area. *ℒ*

Length of growing season under early, normal, and late onset of monsoon in Raipur, India.

Monsoon onset	Recent probability (%)	Av rainfall (mm)	Water availability period ^a (d)			Total growing period (d)	Av rice yield (t/ha)
			Moist I (PE > R > PE/2)	Humid (R > PE)	Moist II (PE > R > PE/2)		
Early	19	1607	7	127	12	146	1.2
Normal	34	1366	14	115	10	139	1.1
Late	47	1044	13	91	14	118	0.8

^a PE = potential evapotranspiration, R = rainfall.

Available soil phosphorus in a rice - wheat rotation after extended superphosphate application

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High yielding rices and improved

management practices have extended rice - wheat rotations to areas with coarse-textured soils and low available P. We found that in rice - wheat rotation, fertilizer P should be applied to wheat rather than to rice, and that if wheat receives adequate P fertilizer over time, P application to rice can be reduced. This long-term study evaluated